

MULTISYSTEM INFLAMMATORY SYNDROME IN CHILDREN (MIS-C) ASSOCIATED WITH COVID-19

Keywords

MIS-C,

Covid-19,

Multisystem Inflammatory

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 in children is usually mild. Recently, a severe multisystem inflammatory syndrome has been reported in individuals <21 years of age. This new disease has been named Multiple Systemic Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-C).

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19, a serious viral respiratory infection caused by SARS-CoV-2, affects all age groups, but is more severe in the elderly and people with additional diseases. COVID-19 in children is usually mild. However, in rare cases, children may be severely affected and clinical manifestations may differ from adults. Recently, a severe multisystem inflammatory syndrome has been reported in individuals <21 years of age. Recent reports from Europe and the United States report the emergence of a new phenomenon associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection with a marked hyperinflammatory response in previously healthy asymptomatic children. It has been observed that some children with SARS-CoV-2 infection develop fever, abdominal pain, shock, myocardial failure and need for intensive care. This new disease has been named Multiple Systemic Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-C).^{1,4}

CASE

An 18-year-old male patient was admitted to the emergency department with the complaint of weakness. The patient's general condition was poor. His vital signs were: Hypotensive (90/60), saturation: 96, fever 38, heart rate 105. During the follow-up, the patient's general condition deteriorated, he lost consciousness, his blood pressure could not be taken. The patient was intubated and started positive inotropes to recover his blood pressure. When the patient's anamnesis was deepened, it was learned that he had Covid-19 infection 16 days ago and was treated in the intensive care unit for 9 days, received dialysis due to acute kidney disease and had myocarditis. Echo was performed on the patient. The ejection fraction was found to be 40. The patient had profound metabolic acidosis. Laboratory tests showed that the patient's creatinine, d-dimer, troponin, crp, wbc levels were high. Ground glass areas in the thorax and pleural effusion were seen in the CT. Upon compliance, the patient was diagnosed with Mis-c. MIS-C is a poorly understood clinical condition described in patients with COVID-19. of MIS-C

DISCUSSION

WHO MIS-C case definition All 6 criteria must be met:

1. Age 0 to 19 years
2. Fever for ≥ 3 days

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3. Clinical signs of multisystem involvement (at least 2 of the following):
 Rash, bilateral nonpurulent conjunctivitis, or mucocutaneous inflammation signs (oral, hands, or feet)
 Hypotension or shock
 Cardiac dysfunction, pericarditis, valvulitis, or coronary abnormalities (including echocardiographic findings or elevated troponin/BNP)
 Evidence of coagulopathy (prolonged PT or PTT; elevated D-dimer)
 Acute gastrointestinal symptoms (diarrhea, vomiting, or abdominal pain)
4. Elevated markers of inflammation (eg, ESR, CRP, or procalcitonin)
5. No other obvious microbial cause of inflammation, including bacterial sepsis and staphylococcal/streptococcal toxic shock syndromes
6. Evidence of SARS-CoV-2 infection Any of the following:
 Positive SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR
 Positive serology
 Positive antigen test
 Contact with an individual with COVID-19
- Although its pathogenesis is not clear, it progresses with findings of multi-organ involvement as a result of uncontrolled inflammation of the immune system and even causes death. More research on COVID-19 in the young adult population is needed to better characterize all clinical manifestations and identify potential opportunities for targeted treatment of inflammatory processes.¹⁻⁴
- Yamazaki Nakashimada MA. Perineal erythema in Kawasaki disease and MIS-C. *Indian J Pediatr* 2022;89:87.
4. Kıymet E, Böncüoğlu E, Şahinkaya Ş. A Comparative Study of Children with MIS-C between Admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit and Pediatric Ward: A One-Year Retrospective Study. *J Trop Pediatr*. 2021;8:67

CONCLUSION

Diagnosis and treatment of patients with MIS-C need to be managed promptly.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

REFERENCES

1. Lee P, Hsueh PR. Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children: A dysregulated autoimmune disorder following COVID-19 *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology and Infection* 2023; 56:236-245.
2. Kara Y, Kizil MC, Bozan G, Kiral E, Sülü A, Kosger P, Kilic O, Ucar B, Dinleyici EC, Evaluation of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) Cases: Clinical Features and Cardiologic Findings, *Osmangazi Journal of Medicine*, 2023;45(2):236-244
3. Sa ´nchez-Alarco ´n MT, Rı ´os-Olivares IE, Gutie ´rrez-Herna ´ndez A, Scheffler-Mendoza S, Gutie ´rrez-Torpey CA,